

1 **Data from: “Acoustic monitoring of anurans and birds in Tropical**
2 **biomes”**

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20 **ABSTRACT**

21 Passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) is increasingly popular in ecological
22 research, but recording and analyzing large amounts of data is still a critical
23 bottleneck for the long-term monitoring of multiple species. The data we made
24 available here is composed of species lists made by specialists' direct
25 inspection of 14,044 one-minute recordings. These data sets were collected
26 across different habitats in South America to evaluate how temporal and
27 spatial sampling effort affects species diversity estimates for bird and anuran
28 communities. These data sets are: (#1 & #2) Generic & optimized sampling of
29 the birds from Caatinga; (#3 & #4) Generic & optimized sampling of the birds
30 from Inland Atlantic Forest; (#5) Coastal Atlantic Forest; (#6) Focused
31 sampling of the birds from Cerrado; (#8) Generic sampling of the Amphibian
32 from the Coastal Atlantic Forest; (#9) Generic sampling of the Amphibian from
33 Inland Atlantic Forest.

34 **Keywords:** Passive acoustic monitoring, inspecting schedules, sampling
35 coverage, sampling completeness, species-area relationship, sampling effort,
36 bioacoustics.

37 **Data set descriptions**

38 We standardized the structure of all datasets as CSV spreadsheets with
39 names referring to their number in the original paper. Each table includes
40 species' names as informed by the respective author in the 'Species' column.
41 All remaining columns represent species' occurrence per analyzed recording.
42 The name of each column corresponds to the name of a soundscape
43 recording, and the presence of a species was coded as '1' and the absence as
44 '0'. We also provide a second version without species' author names, identified
45 by the suffix 'no-authors', for improved readability in some use cases. Below
46 we provide descriptions of the method for collection and other details informed
47 by the authors of each data set (see also Table 1).

48

49 **#1 & #2** *Generic & optimized sampling of the birds from Caatinga*

50 Soundscapes were recorded by 32 ARU (Sony ICD-PX312F, using a 44.1 kHz
51 192 kbps recording resolution) for ~45 hours in Jan-2019. Recordings took
52 place at Açú National Forest (-5.58S, -36.94W), where sunrise and sundown
53 were registered at 5:28 a.m. and 5:51 p.m. (January 20th, 2019). Each of the
54 MP3 files was made with approximately six hours, and the 6-hour audio files
55 were split into one-minute files. A single trained observer listened to one
56 minute every 10 (6 min/hr) for each of 11 locations, taking notes of the bird
57 species present (83 species). Based on the results, the authors applied a
58 reduction in sampling effort in terms of time (days) and space (4 min/hr
59 sampling along the period of highest vocal activity and points) and compared

60 the results to the estimates made with a total sampling effort (6 min/hr.,
61 24h/day). Inspected by Saturnino N.

62

63 **#3 & #4** *Generic & optimized sampling of the birds from Inland Atlantic Forest*

64 Soundscapes were recorded by 8 ARU (SM4, using a 48 kHz 16-bit recording
65 resolution) for five days, from 27th to 31st October in 2019, during the austral
66 spring. Recordings took place at Iguaçu National Park (-25.58S, -54.27 W),
67 where sunrise and sundown were registered at 5:55 a.m. and 6:52 p.m.
68 (October 27th). We set ARUs to record at a generic resolution (6 min/h) for five
69 days. A single trained observer (MJ) listened to the recordings of a single ARU
70 (705 min) and determined an optimal listening period (de Araújo et al. 2021).
71 By focusing on the listening periods, we listened to the recordings of 8
72 deployed ARUs (140 minutes per ARU; dos Anjos et al. 2022). References:
73 (dos Anjos et al. 2022 DOI: 10.1016/j.actao.2022.103829; de Araújo et al. 2021
74 DOI: 10.1007/s10336-020-01812-6). Inspected by Jardim M.

75

76 **#5** *Coastal Atlantic Forest*

77 Soundscapes were recorded by ARUs (AudioMoth ver.1.0) from November
78 2018 to March 2019. During the sampling sunrise varied from 5:12 to 6:04, and
79 sundown varied from 19:03 to 18:54. Each ARU was placed in 48 points inside
80 21 forest patches at least 100m from edges and 200m apart from each other,
81 at a height of 1.5 m on trees. All sampled points are in late-secondary sub-
82 montane Atlantic Forest. The ARU units were programmed to record 1-min
83 every 10 minutes (6min/h) with a total of 144 recordings per day at a sampling

84 rate of 48Khz (16bits resolution). Each point was sampled for 24h by five
85 consecutive days with a total of 720 recordings of 1-min per point. From a total
86 of 34,391 1-min soundscape records, a trained observer (ALR) listened 1,054
87 min (average 74 1-min records per point over the day) and identified the
88 species vocally active at each minute. The data has been deposited at the
89 Arbimon (project Arquivo Bioacústico Catarinense). Inspected by Roos A. L.

90

91 **#6 Focused sampling of the birds from Cerrado.**

92 Soundscapes were recorded by an SM2 recorder, using a 48 kHz 16-bit
93 recording resolution) in 12 points, for two days each point, from 11 to 24th
94 October in 2014, inside Brasilia's National Park. Recorders were programmed
95 to start recording 2hrs before sunrise and 1.5hrs after sunrise (nautical sunrise
96 was registered around 5:00 a.m. for this period), recording 1 min and stopping
97 1 min (30 min/hour = around 1.75 hours or 106 min per morning). Considering
98 12 points x 2 days x 106 min, we have 2,544 recorded minutes. However, due
99 to the malfunctioning of 3 recorders during the second sampling day (3
100 mornings = 318 min), the total time is reduced to 2,226 min. A single trained
101 observer, Alquezar R. D., listened to all recordings and identified species
102 present in each file.

103

104 **#7 Generic sampling of the birds from the Amazon Rainforest**

105 Soundscapes were recorded with ten Sony Icd-Px240 recorders, from the 7th
106 to the 16th of October in 2020, within the Tapirape-aquiri National Forest (-
107 5.87S, -50.50W). Active units were placed at least 250m apart at the same

108 field site. Sunrise and sundown were registered at 5:59 a.m. and 6:26 p.m.
109 (October 7th, 2020). Each unit was set to record continuously until memory
110 space or battery depletion, which resulted in nearly 42 hours of recording per
111 unit activation (MP3; 192Kb/s; 44.100 Hz). A second round of the same
112 sampling scheme was performed in alternative locations in the same field site.
113 The 24h period recorded simultaneously by all units was split into one-minute
114 cuts in cycles of 10 minutes (6 minutes per hour). Due to variations in
115 autonomy and malfunctioning, the final set of 2,880 minutes was reduced to
116 2,388 minutes. A single trained observer identified bird species present at each
117 minute. Inspected by Barreiros M.

118

119 **#8** *Generic sampling of the Amphibian from the Coastal Atlantic Forest*

120 Soundscapes were recorded using Sony ICD-PX312F at five different sampling
121 points from RPPN Gargaú and surrounding fragments (-7.02, -34.96W) during
122 June/2013. Sunrise and sunset were registered at 5:30 a.m. and 17:10 p.m.
123 (June 15th). The recorders ran for 24h for five consecutive days and recorded
124 the environmental sounds by using internal stereo microphones with a
125 resolution of 192 kbps (mp3 format), 16 bits, and a sampling rate of 44100 Hz.
126 The six-hour-long mp3 files created by the recorders were edited into one-
127 minute files. We selected one-minute sections in every 10 (total six minutes per
128 hour) from 04:00 p.m. to 05:50 a.m., totalizing 2100 one-minute recordings. A
129 single trained observer (PRAA) listened to all recordings and identified the
130 anuran species vocalizing in each file. Inspected by Albuquerque P. R. A. and
131 Simões C. R.

132

133 **#9** *Generic sampling of the Amphibian from Inland Atlantic Forest.*

134 Soundscapes were recorded by 6 ARU (SM4, using a 44.1 kHz 16-bit
135 recording resolution), in representative areas of Atlantic Forest habitat
136 heterogeneity, from 9th of October to 14th of November in 2019 in the province
137 of Misiones, northern Argentina. Sunrise and sundown were registered at
138 06:15 a.m. and 06:48 p.m. (October 9th). Each ARU was placed 1 meter above
139 ground attached to a tree, with an average distance between sites of 9.05
140 kilometers. ARUs were set to record a 10-minute period (nonstop) each hour,
141 from sundown until midnight (8 hours), during two consecutive days. A single
142 trained observer (EG) listened to the 1st, 2nd, and 10th minutes of the recorded
143 soundscapes, for two consecutive days (261 min). A list of amphibian species
144 of the most informative minutes, hours, and days was obtained. Recorded by
145 Varela D. and inspected by Gangenova E.

146 TABLES

147 **Table 1.** Description of the ten datasets from Passive Acoustic Monitoring of birds and anurans in distinct Neotropical biomes in
 148 Brazil. Datasets were considered as **generic** (n = 5) when sampling used a 6 min/h rate over at least a 24h period, or as **focused**
 149 (n = 5), when sampling aimed at specific time periods of the day. For each dataset, the following information is provided: the type of
 150 audio recorders, file format, bit depth, sample rate (kHz), minimum distance between recorders, gain (dB), daily period of recording,
 151 biological group, number of Automated Recording Units used (#ARU), the recording rate (min/h), number of hours sampled each
 152 day(#h/day), number of sampling days (#days), and total sampling time.

Dataset	Type	Recorder	Rec Settings	Minimum distance	Gain	Period	Sunrise/sunset	Target	#ARUs	min/h	#h/day	#days	Minutes
#1 Caatinga	Generic	Sony IPX-240	MP3 192 kbps	200m	Standard	24h	05:15/ 17:41 UTC -3	Birds	11	6	24	~1.84	2572
#2 Caatinga	Focused	Sony IPX-240	MP3 192 kbps	200m	Standard	5h	05:15/ 17:41 UTC -3	Birds	32	4	5	3	1629
#3 Inland AF	Generic	SM4	24bits 48kHz	200m	Gain 16dB; Preamp 26dB	24h	05:55/ 18:52 UTC -3	Birds	1	6	24	5	705
#4 Inland AF	Focused	SM4	24bits 48kHz	200m	Gain 16dB; Preamp 26dB	6h	05:55/ 18:52 UTC -3	Birds	8	6	5	~4.67	1120
#5 Coastal AF	Focused	Audio Moth	24bits 48kHz	200m	Medium gain	24h	5:12 to 6:04/ 19:03 to 18:54 UTC -3	Birds	48	6	24	5	1054*

#6 Cerrado	Focused	SM2	16 bits 48kHz	200m	Standard	3.5h	5:00 / -	Birds	12	30	3.5	2	2226
#7 Amazon	Generic	Audio Moth	24bits 48kHz	250m	Medium gain	24h	06:15/ 18:48 UTC -3	Birds	20	6	24	1	2388**
#8 Coastal AF	Generic	Sony IPX- 240	MP3 192 kbps	1h	Standard	13h	5:30/17:10 UTC -3	Anurans	5	6	24	1	2100
#9 Inland AF	Focused	SM4	24bits 48kHz	800m	Standard	7h	06:15/18:48 UTC -3	Anurans	6	3	8	2	261
TOTAL									144				14045

153 * Data was randomly inspected from nearly 34.000 samples

154 ** Variations in autonomy and malfunctioning reduced the final amount of recordings

155 *** The data set was obtained using a 6 min/h sampling rate along a cycle of at least 24 hours but recording two minutes at a time.

156 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

157 GLMR thanks Fundação Araucária for the NAPI Biodiversidade post-doctoral
158 fellowship. CBA thanks CAPES PNPd program (financial code 001) and Consejo
159 Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET) of Argentina for Post
160 Doctoral fellowships. EG, DV, CBA and JPZ thanks grant PUE
161 #22920160100130CO from Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y
162 Técnicas of Argentina. RDA thanks doctoral scholarships provided by CAPES and
163 CNPq. LdA (process 307643/2018-2) and RBM (process 311116/2022-1) received
164 grants from CNPq.